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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Large carnivore monitoring and human-wildlife conflicts prevention in the Ukrainian Carpathians

Cherepanyn R.^{1,2}, Vykhor B.¹, Yamelynets T.^{1,3}

¹ WWF-Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine

² Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, Biology and Ecology Department, Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine

³ Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Geographical Faculty, Lviv, Ukraine

roman.cherepanyn@gmail.com, rcherepanyn@wwf.ua, roman.cherepanyn@pnu.edu.ua

Understanding the conflicts that occur between humans and wildlife plays an important role in the conservation of large carnivores, effective management of their populations, as well as sustainable development of local communities in the Ukrainian Carpathians. Conflicts between humans and large carnivores are decisive for sustainable traditional farming practices (beekeeping, sheep farming, etc.) and for conserving viable populations of rare species of large carnivores in many regions of the Ukrainian Carpathians.

Monitoring of wolves, bears and lynxes, as well as monitoring of the number, frequency and spatial distribution of conflicts between large carnivores and farmers/beekeepers, was established in the framework of the implementation of WWF-Ukraine projects in the model regions of the Ukrainian Carpathians.

The "hot spots" of conflicts in the model territories of the Ukrainian Carpathians were identified, and conflict prevention tools, in particular electric fences, were popularized and implemented among local communities. As part of WWF-Ukraine projects, 36 electric fences were distributed to farmers and beekeepers to protect farms and prevent attacks by large carnivores, as well as 8 video stories about traditional and modern tools for coexistence with wild animals were created and distributed among stakeholders and media from 2019 to 2023.

Understanding the level of conflicts between humans and large carnivores in the region, as well as the number of large carnivores, will make it possible to implement effective measures to conserve rare species, manage their populations, and promote the development and preservation of traditional sustainable farming practices in the Ukrainian Carpathians.

Keywords: large carnivores, conflicts prevention, stakeholder engagement, conservation management, Ukrainian Carpathians

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